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1. INTRODUCTION

In fulfilment of SALTOpower¹ Grant Agreement on the obligations of the Consortium towards the Project Owner (PO) regarding project deliverables, the current document stands as Deliverable D1.5 - Widening Profile Report, as described in the project Description of Action (Part A).

Central to the objectives of the project, monitoring the Widening profile along the project, concurring to raising the research, technical and administrative skills of UEvora staff (SALTOpower objective 2), followed a methodology based on:

- the definition of indicators to identify the starting level (Baseline) of the Widening profile;
- monitoring of indicators related to the Widening profile raising along the project,

enabling a final assessment of the Widening profile-raising impacts. To this end, a Widening profile monitoring methodology with 149 indicators has been discussed and approved.

Considering a wider scoped approach to assessing these impacts, the Consortium has decided to apply the same monitoring methodology to both the Widening (original recipient or measures) and TOP partners, as to ascertain the positive impacts - and motivation - of the Twinning conceptual design to non-Widening partners.

Keeping in focus the main objective of the project - raising the Widening profile - this report presents:

- the methodological approach to Widening profile raising monitoring;
- the results obtained in the Widening partner profile case;
- a description of the main achievements at research, technical and administrative skills in the Widening Partner side;
- an assessment of impacts on TOP partners' side;
- overall conclusions regarding the objectives of the project, in this scope.

2. WIDENING PROFILE MONITORING METHODOLOGY

In accordance with the project's overarching objective of enhancing the Widening profile of the University of Évora (UEvora), the methodology is structured around the implementation of targeted coordination and support measures aimed at enabling the institution to achieve the four pillars of the 4CWC framework: Excellence in Research, Attractive Careers, Aligned Strategy, and Relevant Impact. These measures operationalize the SALTOpower vision of "Widening Impacts" (WI), which is articulated across five key dimensions. Each WI is supported by defined activities, expected outcomes, and measurable indicators to monitor progress and ensure institutional transformation.

- **WI.1** focuses on delivering world-class research in Molten Salt (MS) technologies for energy applications, through the development of a Joint Research Activity (JRA), the involvement of researchers at all career stages (SR, YR, CYR), and the upgrading of research infrastructure.
- **WI.2** targets the improvement of UEvora's research management capacity by integrating advanced project management tools, streamlining procurement procedures, and conducting dedicated training for support staff.
- **WI.3** aims to attract and retain young researchers by providing structured career development paths, access to top-level training and mentoring, and facilitating integration within the SALTOpower research environment.

¹ Project: 101079303 — SALTOpower — HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03

- **WI.4** supports the strategic alignment of UEvora with international research agendas and industrial stakeholders, including participation in SolarPACES and EERA JP-CSP, and the establishment of service agreements and joint research initiatives with industry.
- **WI.5** ensures research results are effectively disseminated, protected, and exploited, through scientific publications, stakeholder engagement events, intellectual property strategies, and the development of a spin-off blueprint.

The methodology provides a coherent framework for the implementation of these impacts, supported by specific performance indicators, including the number of publications, participation in international networks, researcher mobility, training sessions delivered, industrial collaborations established, and progress in technology exploitation. This structured approach ensures that the activities implemented contribute to a sustainable and measurable strengthening of UEvora’s research and innovation capacity.

2.1. Methodology

The methodology developed for this project is designed to strategically support the enhancement of the University of Évora’s (UEvora) Widening profile, in alignment with the overarching goals of the 4CWC framework: Excellence in Research, Attractive Careers, Aligned Strategy, and Relevant Impact. These pillars are operationalized through five interdependent Widening Impacts (WIs), each representing a distinct yet interconnected area of institutional transformation.

To achieve these impacts, the methodology is structured across nine functional scopes, which define the institutional mechanisms and pathways for implementation. Each scope contributes to one or more Widening Impacts and is supported by specific activities and measurable indicators that enable effective monitoring and evaluation.

This multi-scope methodology provides a coherent, integrated framework for enabling long-term institutional transformation at UEvora. Each scope is both self-contained and mutually reinforcing, contributing to a broader strategic vision and aligning with specific Widening Impacts. The clear definition of support measures and indicators ensured that activities could be monitored, evaluated and adjusted over time to maximize their effectiveness and sustainability.

All indicators used for monitoring the Widening Profile are reported in the Appendix 2 where each indicator is related to SALTOpower impacts, pathway, support measures and KPIs. The methodology used measurable (or quantitative) indicators with targets, quantitative indicators without targets and qualitative ones. For the latter, a rating scale was used, as shown in the Figure 1. Below is a brief introduction to the scopes identified in Widening Profile monitoring.

- 0 - NO RESOURCES
- 1 - BASIC RESOURCE DEPLOYED
- 2 - REVIEWED RESOURCE AVAILABLE
- 3 - IMPROVED RESOURCE AVAILABLE
- 4 - FULLY FUNCTIONAL RESOURCE AVAILABLE

Figure 1. Qualitative indicator rating scale.

2.1.1. Scope 1: Proposal Writing

The first scope focuses on strengthening UEvora’s capacity for research proposal development, a key enabler for strategic growth and international positioning. Through a dedicated Proposal Facility (WP4), the institution supports the preparation and submission of R&D proposals at European, national, and regional levels. This activity contributes particularly to WI.4 by reinforcing UEvora’s integration in international research initiatives and its visibility among

industrial partners. Additional support under WP1 includes internal services for proposal writing and revision, with tailored content on dissemination, communication, governance, and project management. Key indicators in this scope include the number of proposals submitted and funded per year, service contracts initiated, budget volume per proposal, and personnel effort (PM) dedicated to proposal writing.

Pathway: Proposal Facility (WP4), Proposal Writing Support (WP1)

Widening Impact: WI.4 (Networking), WI.2 (Project Management)

Main Indicators:

- Number of European, National, and Regional proposals submitted per year: Measures the volume of funding proposals prepared and sent to different funding bodies at various levels.
- Number of European, National, and Regional proposals granted per year: Tracks the success rate by counting the number of funded proposals.
- Number of service proposals and contracts per year: Indicates engagement with industry through research and consultancy offerings.
- Budget and person-months (PM) per proposal: Reflects the scale and resource allocation of proposals.
- Personnel expenditure for proposal writing per WP: Captures the cost invested in human resources for proposal development per work package.
- Availability of proposal revision support and dedicated content in DEC, Project Management, and Governance: Qualitative indicators measuring institutional support to improve proposal quality and management rigor.

2.1.2. Scope 2: Project Coordination and Management

The second scope targets the coordination and management capacity of UEvora's research and innovation activities. Implemented primarily through WP1, this scope contributes to WI.2, by improving the institution's ability to manage complex research projects. Activities include the integration of technical and financial tools such as Gantt charts and monitoring dashboards, as well as the establishment of coordinated internal procedures for project execution. Dedicated training workshops are also offered to support staff involved in project coordination. Indicators in this scope include the number of trained personnel, implementation of integrated management tools, process compliance, and reporting effectiveness.

Pathway: Project Coordination and Support (WP2)

Widening Impact: WI.2 (Improved management skills)

Main Indicators:

- Number of SCC staff trained: Reflects capacity building for project support staff.
- Use of integrated management tools: Evaluates adoption of digital and procedural tools for efficient project oversight.
- Timeliness of deliverables and reports: Measures project execution efficiency.
- Compliance with coordination procedures: Assesses adherence to agreed workflows and governance.

2.1.3. Scope 3: Research Unit Management

The third scope concerns the management and strategic development of research units, especially those involved in Molten Salt technologies. Through WP2, this scope directly supports WI.1, WI.2, and WI.3 by enabling research excellence, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration, and promoting structured researcher career development. The methodology encourages the formation of dynamic research teams involving senior researchers (SR), young researchers (YR), and candidate young researchers (CYR), all engaged in a coherent Joint Research Activity (JRA). Indicators include the number and diversity of researchers involved, internal coordination

efforts, PhD thesis alignment with project topics, and the level of integration across research profiles.

Pathway: Joint Research Activity Engagement (WP2)

Widening Impact: WI.1 (Excellence in Research), WI.3 (Attractive Careers)

Main Indicators:

- Engagement of Senior, Young, and Candidate Young Researchers (SR, YR, CYR) in JRA: Measures human resource involvement across career stages.
- Number of aligned PhD theses and researcher retention rates: Indicates the integration of research and teaching, and institutional attractiveness.
- Frequency of internal meetings and interdisciplinary collaboration: Evaluates internal coordination and cross-disciplinary synergy.

2.1.4. Scope 4: Research Infrastructure Management

Closely related to research unit development, the fourth scope focuses on Research Infrastructure (RI) management and upgrading, essential for achieving WI.1 and WI.4. Through investments and strategic alignment under WP2, UEvora upgrades its facilities to support cutting-edge research in energy storage and renewable gas technologies. These improvements are designed not only to advance scientific output but also to facilitate collaboration with industrial stakeholders. Key indicators include the number of infrastructure upgrades, usage rates, external access by industry, and alignment with sectoral roadmaps.

Pathway: Widening Research Infrastructure Upgrade (WP2)

Widening Impact: WI.1 (Research excellence), WI.4 (Networking)

Main Indicators:

- Number of upgraded instruments and infrastructure usage: Measures improvement and utilization of research facilities.
- External access by industry: Tracks collaboration with private sector actors through shared infrastructure use.
- Alignment with Molten Salt technologies roadmap: Evaluates infrastructure's strategic fit with key research themes.

2.1.5. Scope 5: Procurement and Purchasing Procedures

The fifth scope addresses institutional procurement and purchasing processes, which are vital for ensuring timely and efficient research execution. Under WP1, this scope contributes to WI.2 by integrating public procurement workflows into UEvora's internal platforms, enabling real-time tracking, alerts, and process transparency. Performance is monitored through indicators such as average time to complete procedures, rate of on-time procurement, staff training levels, and user satisfaction with digital tools.

Pathway: Internal Procedures Development

Widening Impact: WI.2 (Improved management)

Main Indicators:

- Average procurement time and on-time completion rate: Assesses efficiency of administrative purchasing processes.
- Staff trained in procurement tools and user satisfaction: Measures capacity building and process quality from user perspective.

2.1.6. Scope 6: Personnel Hiring

The sixth scope is concerned with recruitment and retention of talented researchers. Through WP3, the methodology facilitates structured hiring procedures, aiming to attract both national

and international early-career researchers aligned with SALTOpower's strategic areas. This scope contributes primarily to WI.3, ensuring that UEvora remains an attractive institution for emerging talent. Support measures include transparent calls, competitive career development frameworks, and mentoring opportunities. Indicators include the number of YRs and CYRs hired, retention rates, international mobility, and progress toward PhD completion.

Pathway: Recruitment and HR Management

Widening Impact: WI.3 (Attractive Careers)

Main Indicators:

- Number of YRs and CYRs hired and international recruitment rate: Quantifies new hires and diversity.
- Retention rate and PhD progress rate: Tracks staff stability and academic progression.

2.1.7. Scope 7: Teaching/Research Interface

The seventh scope strengthens the interface between research and education, ensuring alignment between doctoral programmes and SALTOpower's scientific agenda. Implemented via WP3, this scope supports WI.3 and WI.5, by enabling knowledge circulation and fostering a new generation of researchers trained on project-relevant topics. Activities include co-supervision arrangements, training with top-level partners, and YR involvement in teaching activities. Monitoring focuses on the number of aligned PhD theses, access to mentoring programs, teaching contributions from researchers, and integration into partner networks.

Pathway: PhD and Mentoring Activities

Widening Impact: WI.3 (Career development)

Main Indicators:

- Number of aligned PhD theses and mentoring/training sessions: Measures the integration of research with teaching and career development.
- Teaching involvement and co-supervision: Indicates active participation of researchers in academia and partnerships.

2.1.8. Scope 8: Exploitation and Technology Transfer

The eighth scope addresses the exploitation of research results and technology transfer, key to delivering WI.5 and strengthening UEvora's contribution to regional and national innovation ecosystems. Under WP5, the project develops a Spin-Off Blueprint, outlines clear intellectual property protection paths, and engages with industrial actors through joint research and service contracts. Research results are also disseminated in international conferences and publications. Indicators include patents filed, exploitation plans developed, contracts signed with industry, and participation in exploitation-focused events and symposia.

Pathway: Intellectual Property and Industrial Liaison

Widening Impact: WI.5 (Relevant Impact)

Main Indicators:

- Number of patents filed and existence of commercialization plan: Tracks protection and strategic use of research outputs.
- Number of service contracts with industry: Measures engagement and knowledge transfer to external partners.
- Number of symposia/events: Indicates dissemination and community engagement efforts.

2.1.9. Scope 9: Networking

Finally, the ninth scope reinforces UEvora's international and multi-actor networking capabilities, directly contributing to WI.4 and WI.5. Through WP4, the project supports increased participation in strategic fora such as EERA JP-CSP, SolarPACES, and ISES, as well as lobbying for national representation in international platforms. The university also hosts Energy Transition and Regional Specialisation symposia, bringing together academia, policy-makers, and industry. Progress is measured by the number of international events attended, strategic partnerships established, and stakeholder participation in hosted events.

Pathway: Participation in Fora and Conferences

Widening Impact: WI.4 (Networking)

Main Indicators:

- Number of international conferences attended and strategic fora participation: Reflects external visibility and institutional integration in research networks.
- National lobbying actions and stakeholder participation in events: Measures advocacy and stakeholder engagement effectiveness.

3. **WIDENING PROFILE MONITORING RESULTS: WIDENING PARTNER**

The SALTOpower performance and monitoring framework is structured across nine key scopes, each addressing specific aspects of the project's activities, from proposal development to infrastructure management, research coordination, and stakeholder engagement. A key area of focus (Proposal Writing, Scope 1) is the submission of project proposals, both at the European, national, and regional levels. The project tracks not only the number of proposals submitted and contracts awarded, especially those related to services, but also the active involvement of researchers, particularly Young Researchers (Yrs) and Candidate Young Researchers (CYRs), in the proposal writing process. This includes measuring their participation rates and identifying how often YRs take a leading role in content development.

Alongside this, the project places strong emphasis on Project Coordination and Management (Scope 2), ensuring that dedicated frameworks for quality review, risk management, financial execution, and communication are in place and accessible. These systems contribute to a structured and accountable management environment, essential for the smooth execution of complex activities.

A central pillar of SALTOpower is the Research Unit Management (Scope 3) through the Joint Research Activities (JRA). The involvement of CYRs, YRs, and Senior Researchers (SRs) is carefully monitored, with particular attention to how YRs engage in the definition, execution, and assessment of experimental work. Leadership training is also tracked to support capacity building and career development within the research community.

In terms of Research Infrastructure Management (Scope 4), the project follows key milestones such as the preparation of engineering plans and tenders for new "plug-in" components, their commissioning, and the submission of reports on upgrades to the research infrastructure. The relationship with industry is also a priority, measured through the number of service proposals submitted to industrial partners, the percentage of research infrastructure costs covered by these partners, and the presentation of RI updates to relevant stakeholders.

Administrative and organizational aspects are not overlooked. SALTOpower monitors the number of procurement-related meetings (Procurement and Purchasing Procedures, Scope 5) and tracks human resources indicators such as new hires, dismissals, employee satisfaction, and gender diversity, ensuring a supportive and inclusive work environment (Personnel Hiring, Scope 6).

The interface between research and education is another fundamental element (Teaching/Research Interface, Scope 7). CYRs benefit from PhD supervision and structured guidance in aligning their doctoral work with the JRA. Their feedback is collected through satisfaction surveys. Researcher mobility, measured in person-weeks, is encouraged and supported, and both YRs and CYRs are actively involved in developing and submitting R&D funding proposals, including prestigious European calls such as ERC. Additionally, the project supports training through Fast-Track Schools, with participation data helping to evaluate outreach and impact.

On the Exploitation and Technology Transfer (Scope 8) side, SALTOpower fosters strong ties with industry. This includes collaboration on industrial PhD theses, participation of industrial partners in consortia, and engagement with industrial customers. The project also tracks its scientific output, including peer-reviewed publications, articles in industrial magazines, and presentations at international conferences.

Finally, the project places great importance on Networking (Scope 9) and strategic collaboration. It participates in international research forum such as SolarPACES and the EERA Joint Programme on Concentrated Solar Power. It also organizes and contributes to regional forums and high-level symposia focused on national and international energy strategies, ensuring that the project's work is visible, relevant, and aligned with broader policy and innovation goals.

The Figure 2 shows the evolution of quantitative indicators with targets for different scopes.

Figure 2. Performance of quantitative indicators with targets in UEVORA, by purposes, over the duration of the project SALTOpower.

The Figure 3 shows the trend in quantitative parameters for Scope 1 – Proposal Writing, which includes Number of (European/National/Regional) proposals granted per year, Budget per R&D proposal, Number of Person-Month (PM) per R&D proposal, personnel expenditure for proposal writing per WP participation, number of proposals with contents written by Yrs and CYRs. The trends for Scope 1's qualitative parameters are illustrated in Figure 4, reporting on the availability of three key resources: proposal revision support, dedicated specialized content within DEC, and specialized content for Project Management and Governance.

Figure 3. Performance of quantitative indicators in UEVORA for the scope Proposal Writing over the duration of the project SALTOpower.

Figure 4. Performance of qualitative indicators in UEVORA for the scope Proposal Writing over the duration of the project SALTOpower.

Figure 5 presents the trends for the quantitative metrics of Scope 2: Project Coordination and Management, including the number of projects coordinated, work package leaderships, and Project Management (ProM) workshops. For the qualitative data of Scope 2, Figure 6 reports on the status of the Exploitation framework and the existence of a Project Manager profile and position. It should be noted that negative values in the graphs concerning quantitative indicators signify a decline when compared to the baseline values measured at the project's inception (Month M0). For example, with specific reference to Figure 5, the observed negative trends indicate that UEvora coordinated a reduced number of projects and led fewer Work Packages (WPs) over the project duration. Conversely, the accompanying positive trend in the same figure highlights an increased number of project meetings organized by the institution.

Figure 5. Performance of quantitative indicators in UEVORA for the scope Project Coordination and Management over the duration of the project SALTpower.

Figure 6. Performance of qualitative indicators in UEVORA for the scope Project Coordination and Management over the duration of the project SALTpower.

Figure 7 and Figure 8 provide a comprehensive look at the trends for Scope 3: Research Unit Management. Figure 7 focuses on the quantitative financial aspects, detailing expenditure trends across multiple categories: Personnel, equipment, and infrastructure costs; Other direct and indirect costs; Funding from European, national, and regional sources, as well as service contracts. Figure 8 addresses the qualitative side, reporting on the availability of essential management and support tools, including: HR satisfaction inquiries and a "decision tree" for career guidance; Research Unit strategy templates, and access to information on market competitiveness and the State-of-the-Art (SoA); Support for both research consortia and industrial partnerships; Integrated Gantt-based management tools, financial execution control tools, and the periodicity of internal project and financial revision meetings. The observed negative trends in Figure 7 indicate that UEvora received lower regional funding throughout the project duration.

Figure 7. Performance of quantitative indicators in UEVORA for the scope Research Unit Management over the duration of the project SALTOpower.

Figure 8. Performance of qualitative indicators in UEVORA for the scope Research Unit Management over the duration of the project SALTOpower.

The trends for Scope 4 (Research Infrastructure Management) are detailed in two figures. Figure 9 tracks a range of quantitative metrics, such as the increase in revenues, the ratio of IDLE to full operation costs, and the reduction in specific costs. It also breaks down costs by personnel and service days, while tracking the percentage increase in accumulated RI assets and the non-funded depreciation of equipment and investments. Figure 10, on the other hand, focuses on the qualitative aspect, reporting on the clarity and availability of the RI's cost structure and related information.

Figure 9. Performance of quantitative indicators in UEVORA for the scope Research Infrastructure Management over the duration of the project SALTOpower.

Figure 10. Performance of qualitative indicators in UEVORA for the scope Research Infrastructure Management over the duration of the project SALTOpower.

Figure 11 illustrates the qualitative trends for Scope 5: Procurement and Purchasing Procedures, detailing the presence of an efficient purchasing platform and the average duration from a purchasing request to the final supply contract, categorized by the type of purchase.

Figure 11. Performance of qualitative indicators in UEVORA for the scope Procurement and Purchasing Procedures over the duration of the project SALTOpower.

The trends for Scope 6 (Personnel Hiring) are detailed in two figures. Figure 12 tracks a range of quantitative metrics, including the number of listed assets, average recruitment time, and the number of applicants per opening for CYR, YR, and SR positions. It also covers the percentage of applicants from both EU and non-EU countries, as well as turnover rate, talent retention, absenteeism, and average training costs. The figure further reports on expenditure for both internal and external staff, and R&D personnel costs supported by other institutions. Figure 13 focuses on the qualitative aspects of this scope, reporting on the existence of a mentoring program and a clear set of hiring tools in both Portuguese and English. It also details the status of "one-stop shop" support for hiring, strategies to combat endogamy and promote "cross-hiring" with partners, and the use of HR-related incentives by applicants.

Figure 12. Performance of quantitative indicators in UEVORA for the scope Personnel Hiring over the duration of the project SALTOpower.

Figure 13. Performance of qualitative indicators in UEVORA for the scope Personnel Hiring over the duration of the project SALTOpower.

Figure 14 and Figure 15 present the trends for Scope 7 (Teaching Research Interface). The former tracks quantitative metrics, specifically the percentage of co-tutorships. The latter reports on the qualitative aspects, noting the creation of a satisfaction inquiry to measure YR and CYR satisfaction.

Figure 14. Performance of quantitative indicators in UEVORA for the scope Teaching Research Interface over the duration of the project SALTOpower.

Figure 15. Performance of qualitative indicators in UEVORA for the scope Teaching Research Interface over the duration of the project SALTOpower.

The trends for Scope 8: Exploitation and Technology Transfer are detailed in Figure 16 and Figure 17. The former focuses on the percentage of YRs involved in service proposals. The latter addresses the qualitative aspects, including IP protection, patent preparation, and the availability of guidelines for creating spin-off companies.

Figure 16. Performance of quantitative indicators in UEVORA for the scope Exploitation and Technology Transfer over the duration of the project SALTOpower.

Figure 17. Performance of qualitative indicators in UEVORA for the scope Exploitation and Technology Transfer over the duration of the project SALTOpower.

Figure 18 and Figure 19 present the trends for Scope 9 (Networking). Figure 18 details quantitative metrics such as participation in various international and national forums and the number of R&D, policy, and industrial partners. Figure 19 provides a qualitative view, reporting on participation in other scientific agendas and groups.

Figure 18. Performance of quantitative indicators in UEVORA for the scope Networking over the duration of the project SALTOpower.

Figure 19. Performance of qualitative indicators in UEVORA for the scope Networking over the duration of the project SALTOpower.

4. WIDENING PROFILE RAISING ACHIEVEMENTS

The Figure 2 shows the evolution of quantitative indicators with targets for different scopes. It goes from 23% of the set targets recorded in month M0 to 97% at the end of the project (M35). For some scopes (Proposal Writing, Research Unit Management, Exploitation and Technology Transfer, and Networking), the targets set were exceeded, while for the purposes of Project Coordination and Management, Research Infrastructure Management, and Teaching/Research Interface, they exceeded 80%.

4.1. Research profile achievements

Along the project period, the progress in improving the research profile, specifically in proposal writing and quality management, was measured and analyzed. Regarding proposal writing, a total of 16 European projects were submitted, including three ERC Starting Grants, and one regional proposal (SALBIOFUEL), which was subsequently funded. The involvement of Young Researchers in drafting proposals increased along the project, culminating in the full participation of all personnel. As an indicator of this heightened involvement, the Young Researchers independently developed content, most notably for the three ERC Starting Grants. Candidate Young Researchers had minimal involvement, with only one individual participating in the regional proposal.

Throughout the project, UEVORA enhanced its project quality management by implementing the PM² methodology across several aspects: the project canvas, Quality Management Plan, DEC Plan, Data Management Plan, Risk Management Plan, Deliverables Acceptance Plan, and Communication Management Plan. The PM² methodology was put into practice through a series of reviews conducted during the project within the following frameworks: Quality Review (5), Risk Management (5), Financial Execution (4), Dissemination and Communication (5), and Exploitation (3).

4.2. Technical profile achievements

During the project, the progress in improving the technical-scientific profile was measured and analyzed, focusing on project management and involvement in the Joint Research Activity.

Throughout the SALTOpower Project, UEVORA coordinated several other projects (three at the beginning, and two at month 35). UEVORA was responsible for leading 16 Work Packages at the outset of the project and 7 at month 35, demonstrating a sustained leadership role. Furthermore, UEVORA organized a total of 10 project meetings over the course of the project.

The participation of Candidate Young Researchers (CYRs) and Young Researchers (YRs) in the Joint Research Activity was not comprehensive, with their involvement averaging 12 and 3 person-months per year, respectively. Notwithstanding, three YRs assumed leadership roles in the definition, execution, and assessment of experimental work.

The technical proficiency of both CYRs and YRs was significantly enhanced. This was achieved by defining a specific PhD program for each CYR, in alignment with the SALTOpower Joint Research Activity topics. Additionally, they were hosted by top partner institutions, including DLR and ENEA. They also actively participated in all three editions of the Fast Track School as both speakers and attendees, which improved their expertise in molten salts.

4.3. Administrative profile achievements

Within the scope of the SALTOpower project, the OpenProject platform was successfully implemented at CER-UEvora (Renewable Energies Chair). This tool enables systematic monitoring of financial execution, as well as the management of both pending and completed tasks. It also supports the registration of planned purchases and travel arrangements, providing a clear and efficient interface between the researchers' inputs and the procedural tasks carried out by the administrative assistant.

In parallel, the Science and Cooperation Service (SCC-UEvora) developed and deployed a new centralized procurement system, designed to manage acquisitions and projects across multiple research units. This improvement has streamlined administrative processes and fostered a more integrated management approach.

The SCC also strengthened its capacity by recruiting an additional staff member dedicated to providing technical and administrative support for Project Coordination (WP1) and to Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication activities (WP5) of the Twinning projects SALTOpower and Sol2H2O. This staff member contributed to the implementation of PM² project

management practices, particularly in the areas of quality and risk management, which were later extended to other CER projects. Also playing a key role in liaising with the central administrative services of UEvora. Other responsibilities were the coordination of Gender Equality activities within SALTOpower, as well as the organization of project meetings and other events. This included booking and preparing meeting rooms, setting up presentations and attendance lists, organizing catering services in compliance with public procurement procedures, and using OpenProject, in collaboration with the SCC team. In addition, support in communication and documentation management, preparing agendas, sending invitations, managing the project's e-mail account, drafting, reviewing, and archiving deliverables and reports, and ensuring document sharing with project partners. Also, this TADM collaborator managed contacts and supported DEC activities in close collaboration with the project's communication manager.

Furthermore, supported both online and on-site meetings, taking notes, and preparing the minutes of the meeting, being also involved in the PSC meetings, managing quality, risk, and task execution, and preparing PM² methodology documents such as the *Deliverables Acceptance Plan* and the *Communication Management Plan*.

5. WIDENING PROFILE MONITORING RESULTS: TOP PARTNER ENEA

In view of assessing the Widening impact also among TOP partners, a similar exercise has been entailed in the case of TOP partner ENEA, though not all scopes are applicable. In this context, the Scope 1, 3, 6, 7, 8, and 9 were considered, that is Proposal Writing, Research Unit Management, Personnel Hiring, Teaching/Research Interface, Exploitation and Technology, and Networking. Figure 20 to Figure 25 detail the evolution of both quantitative and qualitative indicators, with their respective targets, across several scopes. The figures report on the trends for Proposal Writing (Figure 21 and Figure 22), Research Unit Management (Figure 23 and Figure 24), and Procurement and Purchasing Procedures (Figure 25). Figure 20 provides an overall view of the evolution of quantitative indicators with targets.

One of the main benefits that ENEA has gained from the SALTOpower project is its involvement in the submission of numerous European proposals on the topics covered by the project's JRA, in which the YRs were also actively involved. ENEA has a well-established network of collaboration with the main Italian universities and research institutions in the framework of national projects. However, the network has been widened to include other European partners such as universities, research bodies and, above all, industrial partners.

The Figure 20 shows the evolution of quantitative indicators with targets for different scopes in ENEA. It goes from an overall 70% of the set targets recorded in month M0 to a complete fulfilment (100%) in each scope.

Along the project period, progress in improving the research profile, specifically in proposal writing and quality management, was measured and analyzed. Regarding proposal writing, a total of 10 European projects were submitted (including one ERC Starting Grants) and 6 national proposals submitted and funded. The involvement of Young Researchers in drafting proposals increased through the project, culminating in the full participation of all personnel. As an indicator of this heightened involvement, the Young Researchers independently developed content, most notably for the three ERC Starting Grant.

Figure 20. Performance of quantitative indicators with targets in ENEA, by purposes, over the duration of the project SALTOpower.

Figure 21. Performance of quantitative indicators in ENEA for the scope Proposal Writing over the duration of the project SALTOpower.

Figure 22. Performance of qualitative indicators in ENEA for the scope Proposal Writing over the duration of the project SALTopower.

Figure 23. Performance of quantitative indicators in ENEA for the scope Research Unit Management over the duration of the project SALTopower.

Figure 24. Performance of qualitative indicators in ENEA for the scope Research Unit Management over the duration of the project SALTOpower.

Figure 25. Performance of qualitative indicators in UEVORA for the scope Procurement and Purchasing Procedures over the duration of the project SALTOpower.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The SALTOpower project has successfully executed a comprehensive, nine-scope methodology, culminating in the substantial enhancement of UEvora Widening profile and delivering institutional transformation across the four strategic 4CWC pillars. The disciplined, structured approach yielded outstanding progress, with 97% of set quantitative targets achieved by the project's conclusion, a significant leap from the 23% baseline. Notably, performance exceeded expectations in critical areas, including Proposal Writing, Research Unit Management, Exploitation, and Networking.

The success of this comprehensive initiative is unequivocally validated by profound advancements across UEvora's core strategic functions. Regarding Excellence in Research and Management, institutional rigour was significantly bolstered through the full adoption and disciplined implementation of the PM² methodology across all essential planning and review frameworks. This considerable managerial progress was intrinsically paired with an elevated research ambition, clearly evidenced by the submission of 16 European proposals (including

three highly prestigious ERC Starting Grants) and the successful securing of funding for a regional proposal.

In fostering Attractive Careers and Talent Development, the project successfully cultivated a dynamic, leadership-oriented research environment. Young Researchers (YRs) were fully integrated into the proposal development process, where they demonstrated increasing autonomy and leadership by independently driving key content. Their technical proficiency was systematically enhanced through tailored PhD programmes explicitly aligned with the strategic Molten Salt technologies roadmap, complemented by strategic research hosting at top partner institutions, such as DLR and ENEA.

Concerning Strategic Alignment and Institutional Efficiency, both administrative and strategic functions underwent comprehensive modernization to support long-term research competitiveness. This vital evolution involved the successful deployment of the OpenProject platform for systematic financial monitoring and the introduction of a new centralized procurement system via SCC-UEvora, which effectively streamlined complex administrative procedures. Furthermore, UEvora successfully sustained its external leadership capacity, coordinating multiple external projects and leading 7 Work Packages at the project's conclusion.

Finally, in achieving Relevant Impact and International Networking, UEvora's engagement with the broader research and industrial community was decisively deepened. The university maintained active and sustained participation in crucial international fora, notably SolarPACES and the EERA Joint Programme on Concentrated Solar Power, thereby solidifying the strategic alignment and global visibility of its research portfolio. Additionally, full membership of UEvora to both SolarPACES and ERIC EU-SOLARIS has been formally requested and is currently pending of the national ministerial approval.

The institutional maturity established at UEvora now translates directly into substantial, reciprocal benefits for the project's TOP partners. Firstly, partners can rely on enhanced collaborative capacity. The successful implementation of advanced management tools, notably the PM² methodology and integrated coordination procedures, ensures that UEvora possesses the necessary managerial and administrative rigor for the seamless execution of complex, multi-partner projects. This efficiency directly minimizes the administrative burden and associated risks for TOP partners in future joint initiatives.

Secondly, partners gain access to specialized talent and infrastructure. UEvora now provides a reliable, highly-trained pipeline of early-career researchers whose expertise is explicitly aligned with the strategic Molten Salt technologies roadmap, significantly simplifying recruitment and co-supervision efforts. Furthermore, the strategic upgrading of UEvora's Research Infrastructure creates a shared, specialized asset base, offering TOP partners reliable external access to cutting-edge facilities for collaborative Research and Development (R&D) activities.

Finally, the partnership benefits from deepened market relevance. UEvora's elevated role within national and regional innovation ecosystems amplifies the collective visibility of the partnership within international fora. This, in turn, furnishes TOP partners with new avenues for industrial liaison, technology validation, and market penetration within the Widening region.

In conclusion, the SALTOpower project has delivered a sustainable, self-reinforcing institutional framework at UEvora. This achievement positions the university for long-term strengthening of its research and innovation capacity, establishing it as a highly capable, reliable, and strategic partner for future European research consortia.

7. RELATED PLANS (FOLLOWING PM² METHODOLOGY)

Deliverables Acceptance Plan

The management of the formal customer's acceptance of project deliverables (responsibilities, activities and the criteria for the deliverables acceptance) is described in the *Deliverables Acceptance Plan*. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

Project Description of Action

The *Project Description of Action* includes the project Work Plan and captures all types of resource requirements, schedule and effort/costs foreseen for the deliverables acceptance activities. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS

The Project documents will be stored in a shared drive located on the DLR server in Germany. The access will be granted by that partner, and each user will have a different access according to their profile, role and responsibility in the project.

The Project Steering Committee (PSC) will have access and editing permissions to all folders in the drive. The Project Core Team (PCT) will have editing access to respective WP folders and reading access to the remaining ones. The Project Support Team (PST) will have reading access to WP folders, and finally, the Project Owner (PO) may have reading access to all folders, including legal documents.

In each folder, the latest PDF and Word versions of each document will be available, and the previous versions shall be conserved in a separate folder named [versions] until the end of the project.

At the end of the project, each partner will make a copy of the shared folder to be stored in their own organisation's drive, and this must be kept following internal organisational procedures.

ID	Reference or <Related Document>	Source or <Link/Location>
1	Project folder	
2	Project Description of Action (Part A) <101079303_Annex 1 - Description of the action (part A).pdf>	Project folder
3	Project Description of Action (Part B) <101079303_Annex 1 - Description of the action (part B).pdf>	Project folder
4	Deliverables acceptance Checklist <[29.I.PM2.v3].Deliverables_Acceptance_Checklist.SALTOPOWER.10-02-2023.v1.0>	Project Folder
5	SALTOpower Scope and Success Criteria <SALTOpower_Scope and Success Criteria_v1>	Project Folder
6	SALTOpower Profile Raising Monitoring <SALTOpower_PROFILE_RAISING_MONITORING>	Project Folder

APPENDIX 2: INDICATORS DESCRIPTION

Scope 1 - Proposal writing

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	Target	Unit
Proposal Facility	WP4	WI.4	Development and submission of European, National, Regional R&D proposals	Nr. European proposals submitted / year	Number of European R&D funding proposals submitted annually on SALTOpower topics	Quantitative with target	0.3	Proposals/year
Proposal Facility	WP4	WI.4	Development and submission of European, National, Regional R&D proposals	Nr. National proposals submitted / year	Number of National R&D funding proposals submitted annually on SALTOpower topics	Quantitative with target	0.3	Proposals/year
Proposal Facility	WP4	WI.4	Development and submission of European, National, Regional R&D proposals	Nr. Regional proposals submitted / year	Number of Regional R&D funding proposals submitted annually on SALTOpower topics	Quantitative with target	0.3	Proposals/year
Proposal Facility	WP4	WI.4	Development and submission of European, National, Regional R&D proposals	Nr. European proposals granted / year (year of proposal)	Number of European proposals granted annually, counted in the year the proposal was submitted	Quantitative		Grants/year
Proposal Facility	WP4	WI.4	Development and submission of European, National, Regional R&D proposals	Nr. National proposals granted / year (year of proposal)	Number of National proposals granted annually, counted in the year the proposal was submitted	Quantitative		Grants/year
Proposal Facility	WP4	WI.4	Development and submission of European, National, Regional R&D proposals	Nr. Regional proposals granted / year (year of proposal)	Number of Regional proposals granted annually, counted in the year the proposal was submitted	Quantitative		Grants/year

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	Target	Unit
Proposal Facility	WP4	WI.4	Development and submission of European, National, Regional R&D proposals	Nr. Service proposals / year (year of proposal)	Number of service proposals submitted annually on SALTOpower topics	Quantitative with target	0.3	Proposals/year
Proposal Facility	WP4	WI.4	Development and submission of European, National, Regional R&D proposals	Nr. Service contracts / year (year of proposal)	Number of service contracts secured annually on SALTOpower topics	Quantitative with target	0.3	Contracts/year
Proposal Facility	WP4	WI.4	Development and submission of European, National, Regional R&D proposals	Budget / R&D proposal European	Budget amount in thousands of euros per European R&D proposal per year	Quantitative		k€ / proposal.year
Proposal Facility	WP4	WI.4	Development and submission of European, National, Regional R&D proposals	Budget / R&D proposal National	Budget amount in thousands of euros per National R&D proposal per year	Quantitative		k€ / proposal.year
Proposal Facility	WP4	WI.4	Development and submission of European, National, Regional R&D proposals	Budget / R&D proposal Regional	Budget amount in thousands of euros per Regional R&D proposal per year	Quantitative		k€ / proposal.year
Proposal Facility	WP4	WI.4	Development and submission of European, National, Regional R&D proposals	PM / R&D proposal European	Personnel months allocated per European R&D proposal per year	Quantitative		PM / proposal.year
Proposal Facility	WP4	WI.4	Development and submission of European, National, Regional R&D proposals	PM / R&D proposal National	Personnel months allocated per National R&D proposal per year	Quantitative		PM / proposal.year
Proposal Facility	WP4	WI.4	Development and submission of European, National, Regional R&D proposals	PM / R&D proposal Regional	Personnel months allocated per Regional R&D proposal per year	Quantitative		PM / proposal.year
Proposal Facility	WP1	WI.2, WI.4	Proposal writing/submission support service	PM/WP (personnel expenditure per WP participation)	Personnel months spent on proposal writing per work package participation	Quantitative		PM / WP.year

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	Target	Unit
Proposal Facility	WP1	WI.2, WI.4	Proposal writing/submission support service	Availability of proposal revision support	Whether revision support for proposal writing is available	Qualitative		Descriptive/ Quantitative
Proposal Facility	WP1	WI.2, WI.4	Proposal writing/submission support service	Availability of dedicated specialized contents in DEC	Availability of specialized contents in the DEC (Digital Education Content)	Qualitative with target	Yes	Descriptive/ Quantitative
Proposal Facility	WP1	WI.2, WI.4	Proposal writing/submission support service	Availability of dedicated specialized contents in Project Management and Governance	Availability of specialized contents in Project Management and Governance	Qualitative with target	Yes	Descriptive/ Quantitative
Engagement of YR in proposals/Consortia	WP3	WI.1, WI.3, WI.4	YR (and CYR) participation in development and submission of R&D proposals	Nr. proposals with contents written by YR	Number of proposals with parts written by Young Researchers (YR)	Quantitative		Nr. proposals
Engagement of YR in proposals/Consortia	WP3	WI.1, WI.3, WI.4	YR (and CYR) participation in development and submission of R&D proposals	% YR participating in proposal writing	Percentage of proposals with YR actively participating in writing	Quantitative with target	100	%
Engagement of YR in proposals/Consortia	WP3	WI.1, WI.3, WI.4	YR (and CYR) participation in development and submission of R&D proposals	Nr. proposals with contents written by CYR	Number of proposals with parts written by Career Young Researchers (CYR)	Quantitative		Nr. proposals
Engagement of YR in proposals/Consortia	WP3	WI.1, WI.3, WI.4	YR (and CYR) participation in development and submission of R&D proposals	% CYR participating in proposal writing	Percentage of proposals with CYR actively participating in writing	Quantitative with target	100	%
Engagement of YR in proposals/Consortia	WP3	WI.1, WI.3, WI.4	YR (and CYR) participation in development and submission of R&D proposals	Nr. proposals with contents led by YR	Number of proposals where YR lead the content writing	Quantitative with target	0.3	Nr. proposals
Engagement of YR in proposals/Consortia	WP3	WI.1, WI.3, WI.4	YR (and CYR) participation in development and submission of R&D proposals	% YR leading contents	Percentage of proposals where YR lead the content writing	Quantitative with target	100	%

Scope 2 – Project Coordination and Management

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	Target	Unit
UEvora-SCC are engaged in Project Coordination activities	WP1	WI.1, WI.2	UEvora-SCC are involved in Project Coordination activities	Nr. of project coordination	Number of project coordination activities performed by UEvora-SCC	Quantitative		Nr. project Coord.
UEvora-SCC are engaged in Project Coordination activities	WP1	WI.1, WI.2	UEvora-SCC are involved in Project Coordination activities	Nr. of WP leaderships	Number of Work Package leaderships held	Quantitative		Nr. WP leader.
Dedicated Project Management procedures workshop (by the time of KOM)	WP1	WI.2	Dedicated Project Management workshop	Nr. of ProM Workshops held	Number of dedicated project management workshops held	Quantitative		Total Nr. Workshops
Dedicated Project Management procedures workshop (by the time of KOM)	WP1	WI.2	Dedicated Project Management workshop	% availability of ProM contents	Percentage availability of project management contents	Quantitative		%
Dedicated Project Management procedures workshop (by the time of KOM)	WP1	WI.2	Implementation of PM2 tools	Quality Review framework	Number of quality review framework revisions implemented	Quantitative with target	6 revisions	
Dedicated Project Management procedures workshop (by the time of KOM)	WP1	WI.2	Implementation of PM2 tools	Risk Management framework	Number of risk management framework revisions implemented	Quantitative with target	6 revisions	

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	Target	Unit
Dedicated Project Management procedures workshop (by the time of KOM)	WP1	WI.2	Implementation of PM2 tools	Financial Execution framework	Number of financial execution framework revisions implemented	Quantitative with target	6 revisions	
Dedicated Project Management procedures workshop (by the time of KOM)	WP1	WI.2	Implementation of PM2 tools	Dissemination and Communication framework	Number of dissemination and communication framework revisions implemented	Quantitative with target	6 revisions	
Dedicated Project Management procedures workshop (by the time of KOM)	WP1	WI.2	Implementation of PM2 tools	Exploitation framework	Status or progress of exploitation framework implementation	Qualitative		
Creation of Project Manager role/job position	WP1	WI.1, WI.2	Creation of Project Manager role/job position	Does a Project Manager profile exist?	Existence of a defined Project Manager profile	Qualitative	Yes	Y/N
Creation of Project Manager role/job position	WP1	WI.1, WI.2	Creation of Project Manager role/job position	Does a Project Manager position exist?	Existence of a Project Manager position	Qualitative	Yes	Y/N

Scope 3 - Research Unit Management

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	Target	Unit
Engagement of UEvora SR (Senior), YR (Young) and CYR (Candidate Young Researcher) in the JRA	WP2	WI.1, WI.3	CYR engagement in the JRA	Number of CYR engaged in the JRA	Number of Candidate Young Researchers engaged in Joint Research Activities	Quantitative	20	PM CYR/YEAR (including "in-kind")

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	Target	Unit
Engagement of UEvora SR (Senior), YR (Young) and CYR (Candidate Young Researcher) in the JRA	WP2	WI.1, WI.3	YR engagement in the JRA	Number of YR engaged in the JRA	Number of Young Researchers engaged in Joint Research Activities	Quantitative	12	PM YR/YEAR (including "in-kind")
Engagement of UEvora SR (Senior), YR (Young) and CYR (Candidate Young Researcher) in the JRA	WP2	WI.1, WI.3	YR engagement in the JRA	YR leadership in experimental work definition, execution, assessment	Number of YR with leadership responsibilities	Quantitative	1	
Engagement of UEvora SR (Senior), YR (Young) and CYR (Candidate Young Researcher) in the JRA	WP2	WI.1	SR engagement in the JRA	Number of SR engaged in the JRA	Number of Senior Researchers engaged in Joint Research Activities	Quantitative	3	PM SR/YEAR
How can RUnit leader manage HR: expectations, career development and prospects, team building, create autonomy	WP3	WI.1, WI.3	Definition of HR satisfaction inquiry	Availability of HR satisfaction inquiry	Availability of a formal HR satisfaction inquiry	Qualitative	Yes	Y/N
How can RUnit leader manage HR: expectations, career development and prospects, team building, create autonomy	WP3	WI.1, WI.3	Leadership training	Coverage of leadership training contents	Percentage of leadership training content coverage	Quantitative	100	%

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	Target	Unit
How can RUnit leader manage HR: expectations, career development and prospects, team building, create autonomy	WP3	WI.1, WI.3	Decision tree based approach for personnel profile definition	Availability of "decision tree" tool for guidance on career pathway	Availability of career guidance tool	Qualitative	Yes	Y/N
How can Runit leader define strategy: topic framework, SoA definition, competitiveness assessment, infrastructure needs	WP3	WI.1, WI.3, WI.4	RUnit strategy support	RUnit strategy template availability	Availability of Research Unit strategy template	Qualitative	Yes	Y/N
How can Runit leader define strategy: topic framework, SoA definition, competitiveness assessment, infrastructure needs	WP3	WI.1, WI.3, WI.4	RUnit strategy support	Access to market / competitiveness information	Availability of market/competitiveness info	Qualitative		
How can Runit leader define strategy: topic framework, SoA definition, competitiveness assessment, infrastructure needs	WP3	WI.1, WI.3, WI.4	RUnit strategy support	Access to SoA information	Availability of State of the Art information	Qualitative		

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	Target	Unit
How can a Runit leader establish partnerships	WP4	WI.4	RUnit Networking support	Access to Research Consortia Networking support	Access to research consortia networking support	Qualitative		
How can a Runit leader establish partnerships	WP4	WI.4	RUnit Networking support	Access to Industrial partnership Networking support	Access to industrial partnership networking support	Qualitative		
Financial structure	WP1	WI.2	R&D expenditure	Personnel expenditure	Personnel costs for research and development	Quantitative		k€/year
Financial structure	WP1	WI.2	R&D expenditure	Equipment expenditure	Equipment costs for research and development	Quantitative		k€/year
Financial structure	WP1	WI.2	R&D expenditure	Infrastructure expenditure	Infrastructure costs for research and development	Quantitative		k€/year
Financial structure	WP1	WI.2	R&D expenditure	Other direct costs expenditure	Other direct costs for research and development	Quantitative		k€/year
Financial structure	WP1	WI.2	R&D expenditure	Indirect costs expenditure	Indirect costs for research and development	Quantitative		k€/year
Financial structure	WP1	WI.2	R&D revenues	European funding	Income from European funding sources	Quantitative		k€/year
Financial structure	WP1	WI.2	R&D revenues	National funding	Income from national funding sources	Quantitative		k€/year
Financial structure	WP1	WI.2	R&D revenues	Regional funding	Income from regional funding sources	Quantitative		k€/year
Financial structure	WP1	WI.2	R&D revenues	Service contracts	Income from service contracts	Quantitative		k€/year
Project execution support	WP1	WI.1, WI.2	Technical execution	Availability of integrated Gantt based management	Availability of integrated Gantt chart project management	Qualitative		

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	Target	Unit
Project support execution	WP1	WI.2	Technical execution	Internal project revision meetings periodicity	Frequency of internal project revision meetings	Quantitative	Every 2 weeks	Periodicity
Project support execution	WP1	WI.2	Financial execution	Availability of financial execution control tools	Availability of financial control tools	Qualitative	Yes	
Project support execution	WP1	WI.2	Financial execution	Internal financial revision meetings periodicity	Frequency of internal financial revision meetings	Quantitative	Every 2 weeks	Periodicity

Scope 4 - Procurement And Purchasing Procedures

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	Target	Unit
Development of internal purchasing platform	WP1	WI.2	Technical-administrative meetings alongside project meetings	Number of related TA meetings	Number of technical-administrative meetings conducted in parallel with project work	Quantitative		Nr
Development of internal purchasing platform	WP1	WI.2	Interconnection of different purchasing procedures into unified platform	Existence of efficient purchasing platform	Availability and operability of a unified platform integrating purchasing processes	Qualitative		Descriptive / Qualitative
Development of internal purchasing platform	WP1	WI.2	Interconnection of different purchasing procedures into unified platform	Average nr. Days from purchasing request to supply contract per type of purchase	Average number of days taken from purchase request to signed contract, per type	Quantitative		Nr. days

Scope 5 - Personnel Hiring

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	Target	Unit
Living Facility Amenities	WP3	WI.3, WI.4	Living Amenities Pass	Existence of Pass → MENTORING	Whether a Living Amenities Pass exists, supporting services and mentoring for new hires	Y/N	Yes	Y/N
Living Facility Amenities	WP3	WI.3, WI.4	Living Amenities Pass	Number of assets listed	Number of services/resources (e.g., housing, canteen, etc.) listed on the Living Amenities platform	Quantitative	-	Nr.
Living Facility Amenities	WP3	WI.3, WI.4	Living Amenities Pass	Number of subscriptions → USERS	Number of people subscribed to or using the amenities services	Quantitative	-	Nr.
Hiring procedure	WP1	WI.1, WI.5	Hiring of Young Researchers	Existence of clear tools/documents for hiring in PT and ENG	Availability of bilingual and comprehensive recruitment documentation	Descriptive / Qualitative	-	Text
Hiring procedure	WP1	WI.1, WI.5	Hiring of Young Researchers	“1-stop shop” support for hiring	Presence of a centralized support service that simplifies all hiring procedures	Descriptive / Qualitative	-	Text
Hiring procedure	WP1	WI.1, WI.5	Hiring of Young Researchers	Average time for recruitment	Average number of weeks required to complete a recruitment	Quantitative	≤ 8	Nr. weeks
Local attractiveness	WP3	WI.3	Hiring of Researchers	Nr. applicants/position – CYR	Average number of applicants per position for Candidate Young Researchers	Quantitative	-	Nr.
Local attractiveness	WP3	WI.3	Hiring of Researchers	Nr. applicants/position – YR	Average number of applicants per position for Young Researchers	Quantitative	-	Nr.
Local attractiveness	WP3	WI.3	Hiring of Researchers	Nr. applicants/position – SR	Average number of applicants per position for Senior Researchers	Quantitative	-	Nr.

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	Target	Unit
Local attractiveness	WP3	WI.5	Monitoring of origin of new hirings	% applicants from outside institution – EU	Proportion of EU applicants external to the host institution	Quantitative	≥ 30%	%
Local attractiveness	WP3	WI.5	Monitoring of origin of new hirings	% applicants from outside institution – Non-EU	Proportion of non-EU applicants external to the host institution	Quantitative	≥ 10%	%
Local attractiveness	WP3	WI.4, WI.5	Monitoring of origin of new hirings	Strategies to fight endogamy	Measures to prevent institutional inbreeding (e.g., anonymised or location-independent job postings)	Descriptive / Qualitative	-	Text
Local attractiveness	WP3	WI.5	Monitoring of origin of new hirings	“Cross-hiring” strategy with partners	Joint or reciprocal recruitment strategies with partner institutions	Descriptive / Qualitative	-	Text
Use of incentives	WP1	WI.3	Use of local attractiveness resources	List of RH related incentives (e.g., Interior +)	Overview of financial and non-financial incentives offered to attract personnel	Descriptive / Qualitative	-	Text
Use of incentives	WP1	WI.3	Use of local attractiveness resources	Use of RH incentives by applicants	Frequency or number of applicants who make use of the incentives	Descriptive / Qualitative	-	Text
Use of incentives	WP1	WI.3	Use of local attractiveness resources	Support to applicants for RH incentives	Institutional support to guide applicants in accessing incentives	Descriptive / Qualitative	-	Text
Retention of talent	WP3	WI.4	Retention of talent	Turnover rate	Percentage of employees who leave the institution within a given period	Quantitative	≤ 15%	%
Retention of talent	WP3	WI.4	Retention of talent	Retention of talent	Share of employees retained over time (e.g., after 3 years)	Quantitative	≥ 80%	%
Retention of talent	WP3	WI.4	Retention of talent	Dismissal rate	Proportion of employees whose contracts were terminated by the institution	Quantitative	≤ 5%	%

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	Target	Unit
Retention of talent	WP3	WI.4	Retention of talent	Absenteeism	Rate of unscheduled absences from work	Quantitative	≤ 5%	%
Retention of talent	WP3	WI.4	Retention of talent	Employee satisfaction	Satisfaction level of employees, measured through surveys or similar tools	Quantitative	≥ 80%	%
Retention of talent	WP3	WI.4	Retention of talent	Diversity (Female to male ratio)	Gender ratio among staff, measuring inclusion and gender balance	Quantitative	50/50	%
Retention of talent	WP3	WI.2	Retention of talent	Average Training Cost per person	Average yearly training expenditure per employee	Quantitative	-	€/Pax.year
HR costs coverage	WP3	WI.1	HR Costs Coverage	Expenditure on internal staff	Proportion of HR budget dedicated to employed (contracted) staff	Quantitative	-	%
HR costs coverage	WP3	WI.1	HR Costs Coverage	Expenditure on external staff	Budget share spent on service contracts, grants, or freelance contracts	Quantitative	-	%
HR costs coverage	WP3	WI.1	HR Costs Coverage	R&D personnel costs supported by other institutions	Percentage of personnel costs (especially in R&D) covered by third parties or institutional partnerships	Quantitative	-	%

Scope 6 - Research Infrastructure Management

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	Target	Unit
Development of the JRA (WP2) including a Widening RI upgrade to ensuing activities in Molten Salts	WP2	WI.1	Development of the JRA (WP2) including a Widening RI upgrade to ensuing activities in Molten Salts WP&WT technologies	Engineering plans and Tender for "plug-in" (M17)	Completion of engineering plans and tender documentation for the integration of a "plug-in" connecting high-temp electrolyser and pyrolysis reactor	Milestone	M17	Milestone

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	Target	Unit
WP&WT technologies [WP2]								
Development of the JRA (WP2) including a Widening RI upgrade to ensuing activities in Molten Salts WP&WT technologies [WP2]	WP2	WI.1	Development of the JRA (WP2) including a Widening RI upgrade to ensuing activities in Molten Salts WP&WT technologies	Commissioning of "plug-in" (M35)	Installation and commissioning of the "plug-in" for connection and operation of the high-temperature electrolyser for H2 production	Milestone	M35	Milestone
Development of the JRA (WP2) including a Widening RI upgrade to ensuing activities in Molten Salts WP&WT technologies [WP2]	WP2	WI.1	Development of the JRA (WP2) including a Widening RI upgrade to ensuing activities in Molten Salts WP&WT technologies	Submission of D2.2 Upgraded RI report (M36)	Delivery of the upgraded Research Infrastructure report detailing the installation of the pyrolysis reactor and syngas generation	Deliverable submitted	M36	Deliverable
Financial sustainability	WP4	WI.3	Financial sustainability	Nr. service proposals to industry	Number of R&D proposals delivered to industrial customers	Quantitative	1	Number
Financial sustainability	WP4	WI.3	Financial sustainability	% RI costs covered by Industry	Percentage of Research Infrastructure costs funded by industry	Quantitative	-	%
Financial sustainability	WP4	WI.3	Financial sustainability	Presentation of updated RI (Industry workshop)	Qualitative assessment of the Research Infrastructure update presented at the	Descriptive / Qualitative	15-25 / 26-40 / >40 (good/very good/excellent)	Category

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	Target	Unit
					industry workshop (Energy Strategy Symposium)			
Financial sustainability	WP1	WI.1	Financial sustainability	Existence of clear RI cost structure and information	Presence of a well-defined and transparent cost structure for the Research Infrastructure	Descriptive / Qualitative	-	Text
Financial sustainability	WP1	WI.1	Financial sustainability	Rate of increase of revenues	Percentage increase in revenues generated by the Research Infrastructure	Quantitative	-	%
Financial sustainability	WP1	WI.1	Financial sustainability	Amount of IDLE costs / Full operation costs	Proportion of idle costs compared to full operational costs of the Research Infrastructure	Quantitative	-	%
Financial sustainability	WP1	WI.1	Financial sustainability	% Reduction of specific costs	Percentage reduction of specific costs achieved in the Research Infrastructure management	Quantitative	-	%
Financial sustainability	WP1	WI.1	Financial sustainability	% costs with personnel	Percentage of total costs represented by personnel costs	Quantitative	-	%
Financial sustainability	WP1	WI.1	Financial sustainability	% service days	Percentage of operational days where service was effectively provided	Quantitative	-	%
Financial sustainability	WP1	WI.1	Financial sustainability	% increase of RI assets accumulated investment	Percentage increase in accumulated investments/assets of the Research Infrastructure	Quantitative	-	%
Financial sustainability	WP1	WI.1	Financial sustainability	% non-funded depreciation of equipments/investments	Percentage of depreciation costs for equipment and investments not covered by funding sources	Quantitative	-	%

Scope 7 - Teaching / Research Interface

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	Target	Unit
YR (and CYR) fully engaged in the development of the JRA [task 2.1 and task 2.2]	WP2	WI.3	YR (and CYR) fully engaged in the development of the JRA [task 2.1 and task 2.2]	YR and CYR satisfaction	Level of satisfaction of Young Researchers (YR) and Candidate Young Researchers (CYR) regarding guidance on research tasks along the JRA	Response to Inquiry	Yes	Yes/No
CYR have access to Tutoring [task 3.2] activities with TOP partners and TOP RI	WP3	WI.3	CYR have access to Tutoring [task 3.2] activities with TOP partners and TOP RI	CYR satisfaction	Satisfaction level of Candidate Young Researchers about the tutoring activities for their PhD thesis	Response to Inquiry	At least 2	Yes/No
CYR have access to Tutoring [task 3.2] activities with TOP partners and TOP RI	WP3	WI.3	CYR have access to Tutoring [task 3.2] activities with TOP partners and TOP RI	Nr. Person Weeks in mobility	Number of weeks each Candidate Young Researcher spends on mobility in a TOP Research Infrastructure	Quantitative	8 weeks per CYR	Nr. Person Weeks
CYR have access to Tutoring [task 3.2] activities with TOP partners and TOP RI	WP3	WI.3	CYR have access to Tutoring [task 3.2] activities with TOP partners and TOP RI	% co-tutorships	Percentage of PhD theses co-tutored by Widening or TOP partners, depending on the origin of the Candidate Young Researcher	Quantitative	Yes	%
YR have access to Mentoring [task 3.3] activities with TOP partners and TOP RI	WP3	WI.3	YR have access to Mentoring [task 3.3] activities with TOP partners and TOP RI	Nr. Person Weeks in mobility	Number of weeks each Young Researcher spends on mobility in TOP Research Infrastructure for mentoring activities	Quantitative	4 weeks per YR	Nr. Person Weeks

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	Target	Unit
YR career development through an ERC proposal [task 3.3 and task 4.4]	WP3	WI.3	YR career development through an ERC proposal [task 3.3 and task 4.4]	Participation in R&D funding proposals	Number of YR and CYR participating in development and submission of European, National, and Regional R&D proposals related to SALTOpower	Quantitative	3	Number
CYRs develop PhD thesis aligned with JRAs [1 for task 2.1 and 1 for task 2.2]	WP3	WI.3	CYRs develop PhD thesis aligned with JRAs [1 for task 2.1 and 1 for task 2.2]	Nr. PhD programs defined	Number of concrete PhD programs defined for Candidate Young Researchers aligned with SALTOpower JRA topics	Quantitative	2	Number
CYRs develop PhD thesis aligned with JRAs [1 for task 2.1 and 1 for task 2.2]	WP2	WI.3	CYRs develop PhD thesis aligned with JRAs [1 for task 2.1 and 1 for task 2.2]	CYR satisfaction	Satisfaction level of Candidate Young Researchers regarding guidance and alignment of their PhD programs with JRA	Response to Inquiry	At least 2	Yes/No
CYR and YR have access to Training with TOP partners and TOP RI through Fast-Track Schools [task 3.1]	WP3	WI.3	CYR and YR have access to Training with TOP partners and TOP RI through Fast-Track Schools [task 3.1]	Number of fast-track schools organized	Number of Fast-Track Schools organized to provide training with TOP partners and TOP RI	Quantitative	3	Number
CYR and YR have access to Training with TOP partners and TOP RI through	WP3	WI.3	CYR and YR have access to Training with TOP partners and TOP RI through Fast-Track Schools [task 3.1]	Fast-Track Schools #1 participation	Number of participants attending the first Fast-Track School, rated by quality categories	Quantitative	15 / 20 / >25 (good/very good/excellent)	Number

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	Target	Unit
Fast-Track Schools [task 3.1]								
CYR and YR have access to Training with TOP partners and TOP RI through Fast-Track Schools [task 3.1]	WP3	WI.3	CYR and YR have access to Training with TOP partners and TOP RI through Fast-Track Schools [task 3.1]	Fast-Track Schools #2 participation	Number of participants attending the second Fast-Track School, rated by quality categories	Quantitative	15 / 20 / >25 (good/very good/excellent)	Number
CYR and YR have access to Training with TOP partners and TOP RI through Fast-Track Schools [task 3.1]	WP3	WI.3	CYR and YR have access to Training with TOP partners and TOP RI through Fast-Track Schools [task 3.1]	Fast-Track Schools #3 participation	Number of participants attending the third Fast-Track School, rated by quality categories	Quantitative	15 / 20 / >25 (good/very good/excellent)	Number

Scope 8 - Exploitation And Technology Transfer

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	Target	Unit
UEvora already member of EERA and EU-SOLARIS [task 4.2]	WP4	WI.4	UEvora as member of EERA and EU-SOLARIS	UEvora participation extended to Molten Salts WP2 technologies	Verification of UEvora's extended participation in EERA and EU-SOLARIS networks specifically for WP2 Molten Salts technologies	Descriptive	2 memberships	Number of memberships
CYRs develop PhD thesis aligned with JRAs and in collaboration	WP4	WI.3, WI.4	Identification of an Industrial partner for the "Industrial Thesis" profile	Nr. Industrial Thesis	Number of PhD theses identified in collaboration with an industrial partner for the "Industrial Thesis" profile	Quantitative	1	Number

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	of Target	Unit
with an industrial partner (technology provider) [task 4.3]								
CYRs develop PhD thesis aligned with JRAs and in collaboration with an industrial partner (technology provider) [task 4.3]	WP4	WI.3, WI.4	The engagement of 1+ Industrial technology manufacturer in the development of 1+ PhD Thesis	Nr. Industrial partners engaged in PhD Thesis	Number of industrial partners involved in the development of at least one PhD thesis	Quantitative	1	Number
CYR and YR are engaged with industrial partners in developing project proposals [task 4.3]	WP3	WI.1, WI.3	YR (and CYR) participation in development of project proposal with industrial partners	% YR and CYR participating in project proposals w industrial partners	Percentage of young researchers (YR and CYR) participating in the development of project proposals with industrial partners	Quantitative	-	%
CYR and YR are engaged with industrial partners in developing project proposals [task 4.3]	WP4	WI.1, WI.4	The engagement of 1+ Industrial partner in Joint Project Proposal Consortia	Nr. Industrial partners in project proposal consortium	Number of industrial partners involved in consortia submitting joint project proposals	Quantitative	At least 1	Number
YR engaged with industrial partners in	WP3	-	YR engagement in service providing for industrial partners	% YR engaged in service proposals	Percentage of young researchers involved in	Quantitative	-	%

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	of Target	Unit
services providing [task 4.3]					providing services to industrial partners			
YR engaged with industrial partners in services providing [task 4.3]	WP4	-	The engagement of 1+ Industrial customer to a R&D Service Contract	Nr. Industrial customers	Number of industrial customers involved in R&D service contracts	Quantitative	At least 1	Number
CYR and YR participating in writing project proposals (regional/national/European funding schemes) [task 4.4]	WP4	WI.3	YR (and CYR) participation in Development and submissions of European, National and Regional R&D Funding proposals around SALTOpower topics (e.g. ERC proposals) with	Nr. R&D funding proposals participated	Number of funding proposals (European, national, regional) in which young researchers (YR and CYR) participate on SALTOpower topics	Quantitative	3	Number
CYR and YR have to follow on-line training on IP protection (EU ...)	WP5	WI.5	IP protection - patent preparation	N. IP protection requirement submission/SaltoPower running period	Number of IP protection requests/actions (e.g., patents) during the SaltoPower project period	Quantitative	1	Number
CYR and YR have to follow on-line training on KERS (EU ...)	WP5	WI.5	Scientific and/or industrial exploitation	Scientific and/or industrial exploitation	Availability of guidelines and actions for spin-off creation, identification and protection of exploitable scientific/industrial results	Qualitative	Existence of guidelines	Text/Qualitative
CYR and YR publishing in peer-reviewed	WP5	WI.5	Scientific publications	Scientific publications	Number of scientific publications in peer-reviewed and open	Quantitative	4 / 8 / 12 (good/very	Number

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	of Target	Unit
and open-access journals [task 5.1]					access journals during the SaltoPower period		good/excellent)	
Publication of articles in industrial magazines [task 5.1]	WP5	WI.4, WI.5	Industrial magazine publication	Industrial magazine publication	Number of articles published in industrial magazines during the SaltoPower project period	Quantitative	2	Number
Active participation (contribution) in SolarPACES and ISES International Conferences [task 4.2 and task 5.1]	WP5	WI.4, WI.5	Attendance to International Conferences	Attendance to International Conferences	Number of active participations or contributions at SolarPACES and ISES international conferences during the SaltoPower period	Quantitative	4	Number

Scope 9 - Networking

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	of Target	Unit
CYR and participating international conferences, attending scientific seminars/workshops, following on-line training modules [task 4.2 and task 5.1]	YR @ WP4	WI.4, WI.5	Participation in SolarPACES RESEARCH TASKS	Participation in SolarPACES RESEARCH TASKS	Number of mobility weeks dedicated by CYR and YR to active participation in SolarPACES CSP research activities	Quantitative	2 mobility weeks	Number of weeks
CYR and participating @	YR @ WP4	WI.4	Participation in EERA Joint Programme	Participation in EERA Joint Programme	Number of mobility weeks of CYR and YR involved in	Quantitative	2 mobility weeks	Number of weeks

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	Target	Unit
international conferences, attending scientific seminars/workshops, following on-line training modules [task 4.2 and task 5.1]			Concentrated Solar Power	Concentrated Solar Power	the EERA joint programme activities on concentrated solar power			
CYR and YR participating @ international conferences, attending scientific seminars/workshops, following on-line training modules [task 4.2 and task 5.1]	WP4	WI.4	Participation in other already existing scientific agendas/groups	Participation in other already existing scientific agendas/groups	Confirmation of young researchers' participation in other established scientific groups or agendas	Descriptive	Yes	Yes/No
Active participation (also organisation) in Energy Transition Symposium, Energy Strategy Symposium, Regional Specialization Forum [task 5.1]	WP4	WI.4	Regional organization	Regional organization	Number of regional conferences and forums organized within the SALTOpower framework	Quantitative	5	Number of conferences
Active participation (also organisation) in Energy Transition Symposium, Energy Strategy Symposium, Regional	WP4	WI.4	Regional Specialization Forum #1 participation	Regional Specialization Forum #1 participation	Number of attendees at the first regional specialization forum	Quantitative	15-25 / 26-40 / >40	Number of persons attending

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	Target	Unit
Specialization Forum [task 5.1]								
Active participation (also organisation) in Energy Transition Symposium, Energy Strategy Symposium, Regional Specialization Forum [task 5.1]	WP4	WI.4	Regional Specialization Forum #2 participation	Regional Specialization Forum #2 participation	Number of attendees at the second regional specialization forum	Quantitative	15-25 / 26-40 / >40	Number of persons attending
Active participation (also organisation) in Energy Transition Symposium, Energy Strategy Symposium, Regional Specialization Forum [task 5.1]	WP4	WI.4	Regional Specialization Forum #3 participation	Regional Specialization Forum #3 participation	Number of attendees at the third regional specialization forum	Quantitative	15-25 / 26-40 / >40	Number of persons attending
Active participation (also organisation) in Energy Transition Symposium, Energy Strategy Symposium, Regional Specialization Forum [task 5.1]	WP4	WI.4	Regional Specialization Forum #4 participation	Regional Specialization Forum #4 participation	Number of attendees at the fourth regional specialization forum	Quantitative	15-25 / 26-40 / >40	Number of persons attending
Active participation (also organisation) in Energy Transition Symposium, Energy Strategy Symposium, Regional Specialization Forum [task 5.1]	WP4	WI.4	Regional Specialization Forum #5 participation	Regional Specialization Forum #5 participation	Number of attendees at the fifth regional specialization forum	Quantitative	15-25 / 26-40 / >40	Number of persons attending

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	Target	Unit
Specialization Forum [task 5.1]								
Active participation (also organisation) in Energy Transition Symposium, Energy Strategy Symposium, Regional Specialization Forum [task 5.1]	WP4	WI.4	National Energy Strategy Symposium organization	National Energy Strategy Symposium organization	Number of national energy strategy symposium events organized	Quantitative	1	Number of conferences
Active participation (also organisation) in Energy Transition Symposium, Energy Strategy Symposium, Regional Specialization Forum [task 5.1]	WP4	WI.4	National Energy Strategy Symposium participation	National Energy Strategy Symposium participation	Number of participants attending the national energy strategy symposium	Quantitative	15-25 / 26-40 / >40	Number of persons attending
Active participation (also organisation) in Energy Transition Symposium, Energy Strategy Symposium, Regional Specialization Forum [task 5.1]	WP4	WI.4	International Energy Transition Symposium organization	International Energy Transition Symposium organization	Number of international energy transition symposium events organized	Quantitative	1	Number of conferences
Active participation (also organisation) in Energy Transition Symposium, Energy Strategy Symposium, Regional Specialization Forum [task 5.1]	WP4	WI.4	International Energy Transition Symposium participation	International Energy Transition Symposium participation	Number of participants attending international energy transition symposium	Quantitative	25-50 / 51-75 / >75	Number of persons attending

Pathway	WP	Widening Impact	Support Measure	Indicator	Description of Indicator	Type of Indicator	Target	Unit
Specialization Forum [task 5.1]								
Participation in SALTOpower related fora	WP4	WI.4	Participation in International R&D Fora	Participation in International R&D Fora	Number of participations in international research and development fora	Quantitative	-	Number of meetings attended
Participation in SALTOpower related fora	WP4	WI.4	Participation in National R&D Fora	Participation in National R&D Fora	Number of participations in national research and development fora	Quantitative	-	Number of meetings attended
Participation in SALTOpower related fora	WP4	WI.4	Participation in International Industrial Fora	Participation in International Industrial Fora	Number of participations in international industrial fora	Quantitative	-	Number of meetings attended
Participation in SALTOpower related fora	WP4	WI.4	Participation in National Industrial Fora	Participation in National Industrial Fora	Number of participations in national industrial fora	Quantitative	-	Number of meetings attended
Partnerships	WP4	WI.4	Nr. R&D partners	Nr. R&D partners	Number of research and development partners involved in the SALTOpower network	Quantitative	-	Number of partners
Partnerships	WP4	WI.4	Nr. policy partners	Nr. policy partners	Number of policy partners involved in the SALTOpower network	Quantitative	-	Number of partners
Partnerships	WP4	WI.4	Nr. Industrial partners	Nr. Industrial partners	Number of industrial partners involved in the SALTOpower network	Quantitative	-	Number of partners